

the presence of $\delta(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (due to absorbed water from KBr). The band at $\sim 1540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is tentatively assigned as $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ band. In sodium propionate²⁰ this band appears at 1540 cm^{-1} . This suggests that the propionate is present as a bidentate group, since in unidentate coordination this band is likely to be shifted to higher frequency²¹. The assignment of $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ in the complexes is rather difficult because of the appearance of $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ or $\delta(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)$ bands and also NH_4^+ bands (in the ammonium salts) at $\sim 1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the complexes the bands between 1490 and 146 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned as the $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ bands. The separation between $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ bands thus comes to about 100 cm^{-1} , which suggests that propionate is present as bidentate²¹ group. However, in the complexes containing UO_2^{2+} and carboxylate ion in the ratio 2:1, e.g. $\text{NH}_4[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COO})]$ and $(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COO})$, the carboxylate group may be present as a bridging group. It is interesting to note that in these two complexes the separation between $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ is larger. That $\text{NH}_4[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COO})]$ is thermally more stable than the other ammonium compounds (begins to decompose from 180°), supports the above viewpoint. The presence of fluoride bridging in the complexes cannot, however, be ruled out.

References

1. V. I. BURKOV, YU. I. KRASILOV, V. A. KIZEL, V. A. MADÜ and G. S. SEMIN, *Opt. Spektrosk.*, 1975, **39**, 708.
2. M. M. ESPIGARES J. B. POLONIO and E. G. RIOS, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1975, **8**, 135.
3. V. I. BURKOV, V. A. KIZEL and YU. I. KRASILOV, *Opt. Spektrosk.*, 1976, **40**, 823.
4. C. MIYAKE and H. W. NUERNBERG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 2411.
5. Z. M. ALIKHANOVA, V. I. BURKOV, V. A. KIZEL, YU. I. KRASILOV, V. A. MADÜ and G. M. SAFRONOV, *Opt. Spektrosk.*, 1973, **34**, 994.
6. V. I. BURKOV, V. A. KIZEL, YU. I. KRASILOV and G. M. SAFRONOV, *Zh. Prikl. Spektrosk.*, 1967, **7**, 781.
7. V. A. KIZEL, YU. I. KRASILOV, V. I. BURKOV and V. A. MADÜ, *Opt. Spektrosk.*, 1971, **32**, 1134.
8. J. B. POLONIO, R. LOPEZ, R. MARIA and E. ORIADO, *Av. Quím.*, 1971, **67**, 1193.
9. V. I. BURKOV, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Ser. Fiz.*, 1970, **34**, 672.
10. G. SCHMIDT, C. MULLER and S. OOSTEN, *Christa. Stud. Univ. Babes-Bolyai Chem.*, 1980, **25**, 92.
11. YU. I. KRASILOV, S. I. TROFINOVA and F. M. ISSLED, *Neorg. Mater.*, 1976, **19**, 156.
12. A. FERRARI, M. MARDELLI and E. TANI, *Gass. Chim. Ital.*, 1957, **87**, 1203.
13. A. FERRARI, L. CAVALCA and E. TANI, *Ann. Chim.*, 1958, **48**, 1230.
14. R. M. ROJAS, V. GONZALEZ, J. BERMUDEZ and M. L. DEFAZ, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1979, **32**, 257.
15. V. GONZALEZ, R. M. ROJAS and J. BERMUDEZ, *J. Therm. Anal.* 1979, **15**, 861.
16. M. C. CHAKRAVORTI, M. CHOWDHURY and P. K. BHARADWAJ, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **42**, 247.
17. M. C. CHAKRAVORTI, P. K. BHARADWAJ, S. C. PANDIT and B. K. MATHUR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 1865.
18. M. C. CHAKRAVORTI and P. K. BHARADWAJ, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 1643.
19. M. C. CHAKRAVORTI and N. BANDYOPADHYAY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 2867.

20. E. SPINNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 4217.
21. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, 1978, p. 232.

Cyanato, Thiocyanato and Selenocyanato Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II)

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THE present communication reports the preparation and characterisation of some hexacoordinated mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) and zinc(II) pseudohalides, like cyanate, thiocyanate and selenocyanate with diamine ligands, i.e. propylenediamine (PDA), diethylenediamine (DDA) and *o*-phenylenediamine. The complexes were characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, infrared and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

Complexes were prepared by reacting an ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) and zinc(II) cyanate, thiocyanate and selenocyanate with appropriate ligands in stoichiometric ratios. The complexes were separated on standing and in some cases were obtained through refluxing the mixture for a few hours. All the compounds were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Analysis, conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicate 1:2 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry for the complexes. The complexes melt or decompose above 200° . All the complexes are soluble in dimethylformamide in which molar conductance value was measured. They were found to be non-electrolytes as indicated by their low λ_M value (Table 1), hence all the anions are bonded to the metal ion. All the cobalt complexes under discussion are spin-free with magnetic moments ranging between 4.87 and 5.2 B.M. indicating the presence of three unpaired electrons. The magnetic moment values indicate that the complexes have octahedral geometry around the metal ion¹.

The infrared absorption attributed to $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ for the complexes exhibit strong band at 2205-2225 and bands of medium and wide intensity at 1300 - 1315 cm^{-1} , respectively. These bands indicate that in cyanato complexes, the cyanate is bonded to metal through nitrogen atom^{2,3}. The bands occurring at 2050 - 2080 and 800 - 830 cm^{-1} in the case of thiocyanate complexes indicate that thiocyanate groups are

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Complexes	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M Ω^{-1}
		Metal	NCO	NOS	Se		
1.	CO(PDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	20.20 (20.25)	28.60 (28.87)	—	—	4.87	2.8
2.	CO(DDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	18.90 (18.71)	25.55 (26.67)	—	—	4.95	0.8
3.	CO(OPDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	16.30 (16.35)	23.25 (23.40)	—	—	5.00	3.2
4.	CO(PDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	18.20 (18.24)	—	35.82 (35.92)	—	4.97	2.1
5.	CO(DDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	16.85 (16.98)	—	33.20 (33.44)	—	5.21	1.6
6.	CO(OPDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	15.12 (15.07)	—	29.50 (29.67)	—	5.11	2.5
7.	CO(PDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	14.22 (14.14)	—	—	37.95 (37.88)	5.00	2.0
8.	CO(DDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	13.42 (13.37)	—	—	35.70 (35.82)	4.90	4.2
9.	CO(OPDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	12.30 (12.15)	—	—	32.90 (32.87)	4.95	4.8
10.	Zn(PDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	22.10 (21.98)	28.20 (28.25)	—	—	—	5.0
11.	Zn(DDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	20.10 (20.84)	26.00 (26.14)	—	—	—	3.4
12.	Zn(OPDA) ₂ (NCO) ₂	18.00 (17.90)	27.25 (27.34)	—	—	—	4.6
13.	Zn(PDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	19.96 (19.84)	—	35.00 (35.21)	—	—	2.8
14.	Zn(DDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	18.30 (18.50)	—	32.00 (31.74)	—	—	2.0
15.	Zn(OPDA) ₂ (NOS) ₂	16.30 (16.45)	—	29.25 (29.19)	—	—	1.2
16.	Zn(PDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	15.82 (15.44)	—	—	37.00 (37.30)	—	4.0
17.	Zn(DDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	14.50 (14.61)	—	—	35.10 (35.30)	—	3.2
18.	Zn(OPDA) ₂ (NCS ₂) ₂	13.10 (13.30)	—	—	32.00 (32.14)	—	1.6

bonded to the metal *via* terminal nitrogen⁴⁻⁷. The infrared spectra of the selenocyanate complexes exhibit a strong band at 2050-2090 and the medium intense band at 830-650 cm⁻¹ indicates terminally N-bonded selenocyanate group^{7,8}. The shift of of $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ band from 3405-3380 in free diamines to 3320-3270 cm⁻¹ in complexes is the indication of coordination of diamines through nitrogen atom^{9,10}.

The Co^{II}-*o*-phenylenediamine complexes show two d-d bands at 8600-8950 and 18700-21900 cm⁻¹ suggesting octahedral geometry for the complexes¹¹. The complexes containing propylenediamine and diethylenediamine exhibit bands at 9300-9700 and 20500-22000 cm⁻¹, respectively, and are indicative of octahedral geometry¹² for the complexes.

References

1. B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 12.
2. J. NELSON and S. M. NELSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 1597.
3. D. FORRESTER and D. M. L. GOODGAME, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1286.
4. R. J. H. CLARK and C. M. WILLIAMS, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, 22, 1081.
5. K. NAKAMOTO, 'Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds', John Wiley, New York, 1970, p. 188.
6. J. L. BURMISTER and F. BASOLO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1587.

7. S. M. NELSON and T. M. SHEPHERD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 2125.
8. A. H. NORBURY, E. A. PYDER and R. F. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1439.
9. K. G. PATEL and E. D. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 645.
10. A. BRAIBANH, F. DALLAVALLE, M. A. PELLINGHELLI and E. LEPOZZI *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1430
11. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 324
12. A. B. P. LEVER and D. OGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2041.

Uptake of Organic Acids by Weak Base Anion-exchange Resins

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THE uptake of organic acids by strong base anion-exchange resins has been studied¹⁻⁴ by many workers. Weak base anion-exchangers seem to